

Gender Roles and Identity Crisis in the Poetry of Anne Sexton, a Modern American Poet

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Abstract

The story of identity crisis and gender roles continues as the world is still governed by the binary system of division. The world of today is still divided into two contradictory domains and territories. Some of these binary oppositions are passivity versus activity, day versus night, and father versus mother. It seems all the dichotomies emanate from the primary opposition of man versus woman. Such a division is mainly based on gender where man is taken to be the reference point. The split between male and female is not nature-bound. It is rather culture-oriented in which man manipulates and maintains such a hierarchical and oppositional relationship to perpetuate the subordination of the female. In this binary gender system, it is the female that should carry the negative attributes while the male is established as her constant caliber. Man has the right sole to name culture and define everything including women. Thus, this piece of research attempts to explore gender roles and identity politics in the poetry of Anne Sexton, an American woman-poet whose poetry reveals women's constant search for more meaningful gender roles and a new identity outside the prescriptions of the patriarchal society. This study finds that gender roles and identity of women are molded long before they are conceived in the wombs of their mothers. Patriarchy has already designated roles for them. It has carved out a fixed identity and the rigid roles of wife, mother, housewife, nurturer, and others. However, these man-made roles are not their predestined fate or the free choice of their own. They are, rather, forced on them and dictated by a patriarchal society that does not allow the activities of women to move beyond home. Sexton's poetry underscores the fact that gender roles and female identity are a social construction rather than a biological determination.

Keywords: Gender roles, patriarchy, Anne Sexton, female identity, feminism.

أدوار الجنس البشري وأزمة الهوية في شعر الشاعرة الأمريكية المعاصرة آن سيكستون

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الملخص

إنَّ إشكالية أزمة الهوية وأدوار النوع الاجتماعي ما تزال تتواصل في ظل عالم ما زال محكوماً بالنظام الثنائي للتقسيم. فما يزال الواقع المعاصر منقسماً إلى مجالين متقابلين ومتناقضين. من أبرز هذه الثنائيات: السلبية في مقابل الفاعلية، والنهار في مقابل الليل، والأب في مقابل الأم. ويبدو أنَّ هذه التقابلات جميعها تنبثق من الثنائية الجوهرية المتمثلة في الرجل في مقابل المرأة. وإنَّ هذا الانقسام قائم أساساً على النوع الاجتماعي، حيث يُتخذ الرجل بوصفه نقطة المرجع والمقياس. ومن ثمَّ، فإنَّ التمايز بين الذكر والأنثى ليس نتاجاً للطبيعة، بل هو موجّه ثقافياً، يقوم الرجل بتوظيفه وإدامته من أجل تكريس تبعية المرأة. وفي إطار هذا النظام الثنائي، تُحمل المرأة الصفات السلبية، في حين يُتَبَّت الرجل بوصفه المعيار المطلق. كما يُمنح الرجل الحق الحصري في تسمية الثقافة وتعريف مختلف المفاهيم، بما في ذلك تعريف المرأة ذاتها.

وانطلاقاً من ذلك، تسعى هذه الدراسة إلى استكشاف أدوار النوع الاجتماعي وسياسات الهوية في شعر آن سيكستون، الشاعرة الأمريكية التي يكشف نتاجها الشعري عن سعي المرأة الدائم نحو أدوار نسوية أكثر جدوى وفاعلية، وعن بحثها المتواصل عن هوية بديلة خارج إملاءات المجتمع الأبوي. وتتلخص هذه الدراسة إلى أنَّ أدوار المرأة وهوية النساء قد صيغت سلفاً قبل أن يولدن في أرحام أمهاتهن؛ إذ إنَّ النظام الأبوي قد حدد لهن أدواراً مسبقة، ورسم لهن هوية ثابتة وأدواراً جامدة كالزوجة، والأم، وربة البيت، والمربية، وغيرها. غير أنَّ هذه الأدوار ليست قدرًا محتوماً لهن ولا خياراً إرادياً نابعاً من ذواتهن، وإنما هي أدوار مفروضة عليهن من قبل مجتمع أبوي ذكوري يحصر أنشطتهن ضمن نطاق البيت. ويؤكد شعر آن سيكستون أنَّ أدوار المرأة وهوية المرأة لا تنبثق من محددات بيولوجية، بل هي في جوهرها بناء اجتماعي صرف.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الأدوار النسوية، السلطة الأبوية، آن سيكستون، هوية المرأة، الحركة النسوية

Introduction

Luce Irigaray (1993), a great feminist thinker, proposes that it is only in a different order of meaning and system can women construct a positive representation of female identity. Just like surrealists, as Mujahid Alwaqaa (2024b) reveals in a published paper, argue that our world can be better saved if we conceptualize it in a different and innovative mode away from its sharp categorization and realism. This entails the rejection of the ever-powerful notion of the universal truths including the well-established truth of the binary gender system. Irigaray argues that its universality is a fallacy. It is only universal from the egoistic male perspective (Irigaray, 1993, p. 69). Feminists consider gender roles and identity assigned to women are just social constructions contrived by patriarchy to perpetuate their domination and oppression of the female. So, they try to reinterpret, rename, and reconceptualize the existing culture and theories which are based on patriarchal principles and conceptualization. For example, Sigmund Freud's (1925) psychoanalysis theory poses problems to the feminist project as it ascribes women's inferiority, subordination and identity to their different biology. He states that 'anatomy is destiny.' Based on this statement, the female anatomy of women feminists is crucial in determining their identity and destiny. Nonetheless, they strive hard in their writing to change this misconception and assert that biology has nothing to do with female identity. In their view, female identity is a social construction rather than a biological determination. Furthermore, feminists explore the patriarchal idea that man is the center of the universe and woman is his mere appendage. So, a marginal existence is the only possible location for women living under the authority of patriarchy.

In the opinion of some feminists like Adrienne Rich (1979), it is wrong to extol the traditional female roles because women writers cannot deconstruct the formula of the binary system whereby the female is defined and recognized in relation to the male. They continue to operate within the existing binary system. Therefore, for women writers to define themselves in the light of feminism, they should first investigate the validity of the language they employ in expressing their female experience in a patriarchal society that molds this language to their liking. The process of self-definition is not an easy or comfortable task. In poetry, this process takes place through a linguistic medium called language which is, at the same time, suspect. For a poet especially who is a woman, it poses an additional challenge as she tries to change patriarchal assumptions embedded in the syntax and vocabulary of that language. Such assumptions imply an already patriarchally-constructed definition of the world and the female self and the relationship between them. For a female or any person belonging to an oppressed group existing in a male culture, language reflects

the way of defining or assigning an identity for her. Women's existence in such a language felt to be false. As the female poet accepts the language, she is given without questioning its validity, she is in a way or another accepting a set of capitalist, patriarchal, racist and gender assumptions which are purposefully built into the language so as to deny her of any sense of identity of her own.

Barbara Segnitz and Carol Rainey (1973) emphasize the fact that language plays a very crucial role in furthering the cause of women or sustaining their subordination and lack of self. In their opinion, the woman is trying to look for herself in male literature as subject and looks in vain. She finds that the 'I' in literature is "a masculine consciousness which has become synonymous with the human consciousness" (19). So, what a woman finds in the published literature is not her voice or real character. She discovers herself to be defined as the other or an object rather than a subject. She finds, as Rich (1979) writes, "a terror and a dream, she finds a beautiful pale face... but precisely what she does not find is that absorbed, drudging, puzzled, sometimes inspired creature, herself, who sits at a desk trying to put words together (p. 39). Scholars working in the gender domain recognize that there are cultural, sexual, linguistic, biological, geographical, and psychological identities but the individual identity is perhaps more important than the others (Alwaqaa, 2025a). To achieve a viable individual identity, women writers and feminists should rip apart the binary system on which modern Western culture rests. In this system, the male and the masculine constitute the norm, the positive and the superior. The female and the feminine are, on the other hand, the other, the negative, and the inferior. Irigaray (1998) states that "the feminine finds itself defined as lack or deficiency or as imitation and negative image of the subject" (p. 127).

In her poetry, Sexton is seriously engaged in the act of the exploration more effective roles for women within a system which permits the evolution of the female identity only within its own prescribed parameters. The work of this poet, however, does not aim to discover an unchanging and fixed female identity. On the contrary, the female identity should be distanced from the idea of the changeless and static state. Alwaqaa (2022) clarifies that constructing a fixed and changeless identity in a globalized world becomes difficult as identity is constantly shifting along a plethora of ever-changing factors. Therefore, multiplicity and profundity are qualities which distinguish the identity that this poet aspires for. In her poetry, it is understood that constructing an identity is a subjective process and this process cannot be sharply defined and finally fixed because subjectivity is constantly changing. The female self is a subject in the process of continuous becoming and transformation. The notion of the multiplicity of the female identity seems to be in a stark contrast to its clearly defined counterpart found in the patriarchal system which consolidates the idea of the

unchanging subject and order. Any person who attempts to change this order is stigmatized as a deviant or a rebel. Sexton breaks this order and warns women not to let themselves imprisoned within the bi-polar gender system. Her poems open up new ways for the imagination to invent alternative systems of thought. She realizes that there is an urgent need for change. She should change the way patriarchal culture traps a woman's identity and test the ground on which gender is fabricated. She comes to an important stage in her life and poetry when she becomes aware of the danger of putting on a mask that generates a false gender identity. Sexton's contribution to the feminist movement and heritage is significant as these gender activities become a valuable legacy for generations to come that can be manipulated to enact positive effects and initiate collective social actions (Alwaqaa, 2024a).

Review of the Published Literature

Encouraged by Dr. Martin Orne and being interested in poetry, Sexton began to watch special programs on poetry and attend poetry workshops at the Boston center where she met Maxine Kumin, John Holmes, Robert Lowell, George Starbuck, and Sylvia Plath. The poet Maxine Kumin became another most important friend and interlocutor. Writing poetry proved effective in alleviating Sexton's complex problems. In an interview, she affirmed that she "finally found something to do with [her] life!" (1985, p. 43). In his introduction to Sexton's *The Complete Poems* (1999), Kumin argues that writing poetry enabled Sexton to endure her health problems and prolong her life for as long as she could (p. iv). *To Bedlam and Part Way Back* (1960) was Sexton's first published book of poetry. It garnered good reviews. In 1961, *The Starry Night* was published, and in 1962, *All My Pretty Ones* came into existence, and *Live or Die* was released in 1966. The last collection secured her Pulitzer Prize. *Love Poems* and her play *Mercy Street* were released in 1969 to be followed by *Transformation* in 1971. She published another compilation of poetry titled *The Book of Folly* in 1972. In the year of her death, 1974, Sexton was able to complete three further volumes of poetry: *The Death Notebooks*, *The Awful Rowing toward God*, and *45 Mercy Street*. The last two volumes were published posthumously.

The published literature on Sexton's poetry in general is still lacking, not to mention the topic of gender roles and the identity crisis experienced by women. However, in a Ph.D. dissertation, Alwaqaa (2016) explores the feminist aspects in the poetry of three American woman-poets including Anne Sexton. Likewise, in a latest published article, Alwaqaa (2025b) examines the gender politics and the sense of revolt against the established traditions of the patriarchal society in the poetry of Anne Sexton and other feminists. With the exception of these studies, the researcher

could not find other published academic papers that tackle themes in Sexton's poetry except for some short articles in newspapers and short reviews in magazines. Thus, this piece of research attempts to bridge the knowledge gap existing in the published literature and aims to bring genders issues and identity politics embedded in Sexton's poetry into the limelight.

Discussion and Analysis

Sexton writes in one of her letters: "I run around begging everyone to approve and like me and then sneak back to my desk and write this stuff that people either adore or detest" (2004, p. 67). The stuff she constructs is not romantic or poems speaking of the joys of motherhood and the greatness of being the submissive wife. She writes poems that come from the dark recesses of her heart, and her destructive and oppressive life. While writing poetry does not provide all the answers, Sexton finds it to be a valuable tool for self-exploration and self-identification. She explains, "It is the split self, it seems to, that is the mad woman. When writing you make a new reality and become whole... the creative mind is the analyst who gives pattern and meaning to what the persona sees as only incoherent experience" (1992, p. 64). However, while writing is useful for creating an identity beyond the traditional roles of wife and mother; it is also deeply problematic in terms of those roles. Sexton later admits, "I realize, with guilt, that I am a woman, that it should be for the children, or my husband, or my home – not writing. ... I do love my children but I am not feminine enough to be all lost in their care" (ibid.). Yet, writing poetry for Sexton appears to expose some true aspects of her real self and identity as she herself states, "I wonder if the artist ever lives his life – he is so busy recreating it To create is to live. To perform is essentially false. Only as I write do I realize myself. I don't know what that does to life" (2004, p. 382).

Woman, in most societies, defines herself through interpersonal relationships and her dependence on patriarchy is a marked tendency in those hardline patriarchal societies. The dominant psycho-social realities which determine a woman's identity find expression in literature as role-models. A woman transforms her cultural devaluation of her talents and capabilities into feelings of unworthiness and inferiority as these feelings epitomized in the poetry of Sexton. Interpersonal relationships are structured to maintain hierarchical relationships between the sexes. In some societies the structures are so rigidly set that even accomplished women find it difficult to create complimentary roles for themselves or eke out an identity of their own. Therefore, a woman's life is a dehumanizing and humiliating experience in a patriarchal society. The struggle to become a human being is the necessary fate that awaits a woman. This struggle is manifested in women's literature in manifold forms. In women's poetry the persona assumes different forms corresponding

to the various roles a woman is forced to assume. The different guises the persona assumes lead to multiple voices and a complex fabric of identities in which she cannot resolve which identity she should assimilate. In addition to the various roles of wife, daughter, and mother, a woman poet finds herself forced to act out the roles of unhappy woman, selfless lover, unseated mistress, reluctant nymphomaniac, innocuous doll, vicious seductress and ferocious witch.

Sexton undergoes an identity crisis due to her inability to establish meaningful and abiding relationships with the world around her. She attempts to resolve this crisis either through adventurous love or by writing poetry, wherein the urge to return to the past becomes, in essence, an occasion for the celebration of the body. Unfortunately, her incapacity to solve this crisis resulted in self-destruction and self-annihilation. In her recent biography of Anne Sexton, Diane Wood Middlebrook has transcribed Sexton's conversation with Martin Orne from the audiotape of a therapy session, "I suspect that I have no self. So, I produce a different one for different people. I don't believe me, and I seem forced to constantly establish long fake and various personalities" (1991, pp. 62-3). This confession indicates the nature of Sexton's conflictual relationships characterized by a deep crisis of identity. All the inter-personal relationships which she is involved in give insights into the socio-psychological complexity of living as a woman in a patriarchal society. She builds up a separate self to nurture each relationship and to abandon or repress it later when the relationship is made or done. A sense of skepticism of the significance of each relationship and a streak of guilt pervade all her relationships, with the exception, perhaps, of her relationship with Martin Orne. Middlebrook observes that Sexton's tendency to sexualize her significant relationships, appears to be a habit which makes up a clinical picture of the poet as a woman undergoing sexual trauma. Sexton mystifies facts and memories and even parades and mixes fictional relationships in her poems. This seems to be a reflection on her pathologically unbalanced mind with untapped creative potential.

In "Mother and Jack and the Rain," Sexton experiences the same identity crisis found in Nana poems and this poem is apparently dealing with the historical Oedipus myth. The speaker identifies herself with the mother. She feels the father's kiss but inhabits the mother's heart. Here the message conveyed seems to be that woman is reduced to the medium for man's journey. The sailor's booty takes the form of mother's body concealed from the daughter by the wall through which the father can reach the girl. Jack comes to stand for the father. As the girl obtains womanhood, probably at the initiation of the father, her mother is dead. The central conflict in the poem revolves around the haunting and cursing of the rain outside and the affirming and endorsing of the poet's identity

inside. Ultimately the tensions are resolved by writing poetry becomes for the speaker the daily bread and place of worship and self-exploration. So, the authorial identity often seems to overwhelm the other forms of identifications and of prior significance to the poet. By composing the fragments of the poem, the speaker is in a sense composing her real identity. The thematic and formal significances of rituals of mastery are combined in the poem.

With this pen I take in hand my selves
and with these dead disciples I will grapple.
Though rain curses the window
let the poem be made (*The Complete Poems*, 1999, p. 109).¹

Composing a poem for Sexton becomes a ritual as it offers her an opportunity to find her true self. She writes against the desires of a male authority. The speaker identifies with her female body which is seen by patriarchy as a source of shame. The speaker's mother becomes dead either in thought or in feeling as the mother represents the patriarchal ideology.

In "Christmas Eve", Sexton cogitates on the hung picture of her mother. She sits alone musing over the portrait of the deceased mother as she is sipping 'Christmas brandy' late at night. The problem of the identification is evident.

I sat up drinking the Christmas brandy,
watching your picture,
letting the tree move in and out of focus.
the bulbs vibrated.
they were a halo over your forehead (CPS, p. 139).

The speaker temporarily attains peace as she sees herself reflected in this image as both daughter and mother. Sexton strategically invents a Christian ritual to seek forgiveness of the mother and to initiate a personal journey of self-exploration. There is a sense of guilt and anguish at her remembrance of the mother.

I saw you as you were.
Then I thought of your body
as one thinks of murder... (CPS, p. 140).

Again, the body is identified with the mother. She recalls her mother's cancer and death.

I touched a present for the child,

¹ All the poems have been taken from the same source. Henceforth, this reference is abbreviated to CPS.

the last I bred before your death;
and then I touched my breast
and then I touched the floor
and then my breast again as if,
somehow, it were one of yours (CPS, p. 140).

The breast is at once the symbol of life-giving milk and death-dealing cancer. The last part of the poem is the verbal performance of a rite. It is a recurring technique in Sexton's poetry that she identifies Nana or her mother or her daughter through her identification with the female body. In its final sickness, the body of the speaker's mother murdered its identity; however, the same body generates the living body and identity of the speaker-daughter. It is through body, through motherhood that the identities of various generations are evolved.

So, the female body and the essence of womanhood have become important sites for power and identification in Sexton's poetry. As many of Sexton's poems investigate the female identity in relation to women's traditional roles and patriarchal ideology, "In Celebration of my Uterus," she proudly celebrates female identity in spite of the fact that many readers and critics commonly complain that Sexton's work in general is so full of despair, depression, uncertainty, and death. This poem was written after one of her doctors proposed that she may have a hysterectomy. In studying gender identity as linked to biology, female sexual reproductive organs have been the crucial factor in women's conception of themselves and the world around them. Such organs are employed by feminist poets as a synecdoche to emphasize womanhood and to investigate female identity. Polivy thinks that "a threat to (reproductive) organs can easily constitute a threat to a woman's whole self-concept of femininity" (417). While biological essentialist theories have justifiably been the subject of much criticism, the body does seem to play an important role in establishing female identity.

In the case of "In Celebration of my Uterus," the biological aspect of womanhood and female identity is highlighted and celebrated. In one of Sexton's letters to Robert Bly, she writes, "today is a special day for me.... Day before yesterday they were going to give me a hysterectomy but yesterday I went to some big deal specialist in Boston and I can keep it. So saved is a part of the soul of the woman who lives in me" (2004, 302). The poem begins with an image that can be interpreted as the potential for new life and the source of vitality and mobility. The speaker proclaims to her public readership that

Everyone in me is a bird.

I am beating all my wings.
They wanted to cut you out
but they will not.
They said you were immeasurably empty
but you are not.
They said you were sick unto dying
but they were wrong.
You are singing like a school girl.
You are not torn (CPS 181-2).

The poet defiantly reaffirms that her reproductive organ, the uterus, which the doctors told her that is “immeasurably empty” and “sick unto dying,” is in reality “not torn” or unhealthily affected. Repetition of similar propositional lines such as “they will not,” “you are not,” “they were wrong,” and “you are not torn” emphasizes the triumphant and celebratory tone of the poem and the necessity for self-assertion. Her uterus and its potential to produce life is a part of her essential female identity, and she personifies and apostrophizes the uterus by directly and intimately addressing it as if speaking to a beloved one in the second stanza.

Sweet weight,
in celebration of the woman I am
and of the soul of the woman I am
and of the central creature and its delight
I sing for you. I dare to live.
Hello, spirit. Hello, cup.
Fasten, cover. Cover that does contain.
Hello to the soil of the fields.
Welcome, roots (CPS 182).

These lines are very positive, and the tone is victorious, enhancing the analysis that this celebration is not only of a body part but of the poet's identity as woman, of "the soul" of the woman she is, of "the central creature and its delight." The life-giving aspect of women is asserted with "I sing for you. I dare to live" and images of fertility and generation are underscored in metaphorical descriptions of "the soil of the fields" and "roots." The mundane, fertile image is reinforced later in the poem with words such as "plant" and "harvest," and some of the images have almost primitive, ritual connotations, such as "let me drum," "let me carry bowls for the offering" and "let

me make certain tribal figures." So, in its totality, these images effectively boil down to the fact that Sexton's female organs are substantially her identity.

Therefore, this poem is a tribute to women who, as a whole community, are created and celebrated in words in honor of their femaleness, as the line "Many women are singing together of this," transparently suggests. A variety of multi-national women all over the world have been listed in the poem engaging in various occupations and activities, yet united by their sense of womanhood and biological identity. According to Ostriker, this poem finds unity where the culture propagates division between a woman's sexuality and her spirituality, her creativity and her procreativity, herself and other women, her private and public self (1986: 111). Thus, the similarities among women of various geographies in terms of their jobs, roles and destinies are highlighted, extending from the specific image of "one is straddling a cello in Russia" or "one is stretching on her mat in Thailand" to the more universal delineation,

one is
anywhere and some are everywhere and all
seem to be singing, although some can not
sing a note (CPS 182).

The women mentioned within the lines of this poem encompass a wide range of female age groups from the young "nineteen-year-olds" to a mother who is "wiping the ass of her child" to one who is "dying but remembering a breakfast." In this celebratory poem, womanhood assumes more importance than age, occupation or nationality. The poem concludes with one word, "yes," forming the last line and reaffirming the communal identity of women all over the world. While so many of Sexton's poems are replete with uncertainty and hesitation, this short, decisive, and positive ending calls and encourages women to celebrate their femaleness and their procreative powers.

However, this poem received mixed responses, both positive and negative. Charlotte Otten (1986) notes that, "In Celebration of My Uterus" Sexton not only wrote "what was considered by many an outrageous poem on an unseemly subject, but she went on the poetry circuit and read this poem to mixed audiences... the first shock was felt round the world" (p. xxi). While this poem obviously addresses female anatomy, one may ask: why is it so outrageous? The only line that uses any kind of vulgar language is the one which mentions "wiping the ass of her child," but this is crude that fits in with the earthly maternal feel of the poem. This poem, no doubt, made a shock at the time it was written when such topics were less frequently discussed. Today; however, there are several female poets who write poems on similar topics in a much more frank and graphic manner.

In his "Foreword" to Sexton's *Complete Poems*, Maxine Kumin (1999) praises her for the paving the way for women to write about such subjects. He writes.

Women poets in particular owe a debt to Anne Sexton, who broke new ground, shattered taboos, and endured a barrage of attacks along the way because of the flamboyance of her subject matter, which, twenty years later, seems far less daring. She wrote about menstruation, abortion... incest, adultery, and drug addiction at a time when the proprieties embraced none of these as proper topics for poetry. Today, the remonstrances seem almost quaint. Anne delineated the problematic position of women – the neurotic reality of the time – though she was not able to cope in her own life with the personal trouble it created (p. xix).

As Kumin notes, what was once considered shocking is far more common and acceptable in poetry today, although not all readers approve of such candid writing about the female body.

Along the same lines, the poem entitled "45 Mercy Street" displays the portraits of the artist as a young lady whose femaleness is a source of identity. The poem is based on the context of the twenty third Psalm from the Bible. Sexton writes, "Surely goodness and mercy shall/ follow me all my days of my life." In these two lines, the poet playfully stresses the words "surely" and "mercy." The poem's ultimate message is to express the wonderful female capacity for compassion, the female ability to accept and forgive. The personae of the poem are all female; the daughters, mother, the grandmother, Nana, and friends with whom the speaker seeks to identify as Linda Wagner-Martin (1989) states that "...the poet, unable to find independence in marriage, turns to her womanliness as her chief identity" (p. 160). The poem is replete with a sense of irony that mainly lies in the statement of the disillusioned speaker identified as married Anne; "this is no dream / just my oily life." So, the speaker divulges her frustration and anger.

Who wants to own the past
That went out on a deep ship
And left me only with paper? (CPS 483).

In the end, the poet is abandoned with her only consolation and devising to mould an identity for herself.

I live in,
my life,
and its hauled up
notebooks (CPS 484).

In "The Double Image", the speaker splits herself between the doubles of her mother and her daughter (CPS. 35-42). Having found it difficult to establish an identity for herself, the speaker judges herself with the double images of mother and daughter, yet the speaker feels guilty about her attempt to piece her life together through double images. She believes that she may get along well because of her children. They make her feel herself, but she ultimately cannot cope up with these strategies that may keep her out of self-disintegration and destruction. However, in "Suicide Note," Sexton highlights the tragedy of being a woman. She states that it is "far better / not to be born twice. / It is better not to be born a woman" (CPS. 156-9).

In contrast to "Suicide Note," and "Double Image," "The Fortress" is a poem that reveals the bittersweet memory and dangerous hidden connections between mother and daughter. The poem explores the theme of communal identity, female community and solidarity rather than individuality. The traditional notion of the extended family is powerfully presented in the poem. The title suggests a lion defense against the external threat. The poet creates images as a defense mechanism, as a kind of cure and self-identification. The sleeping child's wishes elude the mother. They are both cut off from an assured future.

Darling, life is not in my hands:
life with its terrible changes
will take you, bombs or glands,
your own child at
your breast, your own house on your own land.
Outside the bittersweet turns orange.
Before she died, my mother and I picked those fat
branches, finding orange nipples
on the gray wire strands.

We weeded the forest, curing trees like cripples (CPS 67).

Sexton believes that the love between the mother and the daughter has greater redemptive power than any religious faith. It is clear that the speaker has a sense of her own value as a mother; "What ark / can I fill for you when the world goes wild?" Despite the fact that she 'cannot promise' that her daughter's wish will be fulfilled, the poem accentuates their domestic alliance, their togetherness and their common identification, which forms a 'fortress' against 'the bombs' of experience. The shared experience of the past is an abiding memory.

I give you the images I know.

we laugh and we touch.

I promise you love.

Time will not take away that (CPS 67).

Sexton's ambivalent attitude creates an internal conflict between the identity of being a poet or a housewife. In her letter to Doctor Orne, her therapist, she furiously goes as far as to protest: "You so winningly said 'People come first' meaning before the writing. You forced me to say the truth. The writing comes first" (2004, p. 349). While this is a harsh criticism, juggling the demanding roles of a typical woman and writer is a common theme in female personal poetry, that is to say a conflict between an authorial identity and the traditional roles of woman will never cease. To be a writer and at the same time a wife and mother are strenuous and time-consuming. These challenging activities of pursuing both tasks simultaneously appear frequently to lead to guilt and resentment in the writer and feelings of abandonment or neglect in the members of the family. For the personal and feminist poet this crisis of coping with the responsibilities of these occupations is aggravated by possible disapproval from family, friends and readers not only of the activity of writing, but also the themes and subjects which are discussed in the writing itself. Because of these contradictory impulses and obligations, female writers of personal poetry can feel as if they are split into two irreconcilable identities. In "Vesuvius at Home: The Power of Emily Dickinson," Adrienne Rich (1979) states.

It is extremely painful and dangerous way to live – split between a publicly acceptable persona and a part of yourself that you perceive as the essential, the creative and powerful self, yet also as possibly unacceptable, perhaps even monstrous.... For many women the stresses of this splitting have led, in a world so ready to assert our innate passivity and to deny our independence and creativity, to extreme consequences: the mental asylum, self-imposed silence, recurrent depression, suicide, and often severe loneliness (p. 114).

Sexton's poetic successes serve to create more tension in her home life, with her husband once tearing up her poetry and throwing her typewriter across the room (Middlebrook, 1992, p. 80). However, she is not willing to give up something that is helping her to reach some idea of a separate self and personal achievement that domestic life simply cannot provide. And after all, why should it be a choice between writer or wife and mother? This conflict of devotion and identification is manifested in Alicia Ostriker's (1983) statement, "That women should have babies rather than books is the considered opinion of Western Civilization. That women should have books rather than babies is a variation on that theme. Is it possible, or desirable, for a woman to have both" (p.

162).

Likewise, Sexton could not accept the roles of wife and mother as her own identity because it was not the personal fulfillment that she searched for in her life. Something stirred within her that desired more than changing poopy pants, cooking supper, and cleaning the house. The desire to weave words into inflammable ideas burns in her heart. To write in her own voice and makes poetry is her ultimate dream and relief. She experiences the same feeling that Plath (2000) vehemently expresses in one of her journal entries: "My happiness streams from having wretched a piece out of my life, a piece of hurt and beauty, and transformed it to typewritten words on paper? How can he know I am justifying my life, my keen emotion, my feeling, by turning it into print?" (p. 22). Poetry is her life, her savior, and her redeemer, as Sexton clearly states in one of her letters: "The thing that seems to be saving me is the poetry" (2004, p. 51). So, poetry is a place where she is in control and where she can only belong to her words. In relation to her search for her identity, Sandra Gilbert (1977) proposes that Sexton wrote to carve her own paths on the road to self-definition. If she can define her life through poetry, she can discover her lost identity. Gilbert states that Sexton writes "in the hope of discovering or defining a self, a certainty, a tradition"(p. 446). The spirit of the writer, Therefore, would hopefully be the missing piece to her lost identity; however, to be a writer was not a woman's role in the patriarchal literary canon. Men fill the academia roles, the professional roles, the writer roles, and there is no place left for a woman. This poet feels uneasy in the roles of wife and mother. Her passion seems to be her doom, couched in her words. She writes only to be rejected in the role of writer. She strives for an identity that society would not allow her.

Sexton does not come to a safe anchor regarding her true identity, her identifications with people within and around her are momentary and unstable. She strives hard to discover herself and solve the persistent question of identity, but her efforts come to a total failure. She struggles to find words and manipulate them for her own purpose so as to construct a new perspective and an identity in her own terms. She composes a poem titled "words" in which she explores her female identity as a poet in relation with language. Words for her are very important tools in fulfilling her life and filling the empty crevices of her mind. It seems that words control her rather than controlling them. They, simultaneously, become her savior and condemner. She writes, "Be careful of words, / even the miraculous ones" (CPS, p. 463). In her work, Sexton reaches at a point when she becomes weary of words because they do not provide her with solutions to her psychological traumas, social problems and mental disintegration. In her poem "Ambition Bird," she decides to give up the life

of words. she writes, "I must get a new bird / and a new immortality box. / There is folly enough inside this one" (CPS, p. 300). She is actually hesitant about her situation because she is not clear about what she exactly wants. She is severely torn between her role as a writer and her role as a housewife. In this poem, she seems to deny the part of her self that writes. She longs for a simple life.

Nonetheless, the life of this poet is never a simple one. Words control her minds; words are the imprints on her hearts. Poetry was the identity that is placed upon her lives. She writes what others cannot describe. She writes poems that make the world blush. The world and the time she lived in was simply not ready for this scandalous woman and her daring poems speaking of female genitalia, sexual inhibitions and female wishes. Sexton defies the norm as she states in one of her letters that such women "are damned for being tragic and confessional constantly from both sides of the ocean..." (2004, p. 278). Confessional literature is quite similar to autobiographical literature; however, the former entails the confessions of private life whereas the latter is, according to Yahya Dahami (2025), focusses on writing the self.

Thus, it seems clear and inevitable for this woman writer to reclaim words and images and the way they are put together. She feels the dire necessity to revise the whole tradition of poetry and repossess and reinhabit the male-constructed language. This involves a gradual and strenuous process of renaming and reviewing that language. This process applies not only to Sexton but also to a number of modern American female poets. Therefore, five stages are essentially required in the process of renaming and redefining the traditional concepts of gender identity. Most groups which are designated by society as the 'other' need to work through these stages in the establishment and progress toward a real female voice and a true self wholly their own. This is true not only of poetry but in general of the literature of the dispossessed and the excluded such as women and slaves. In a paper on the power of literary discourse on furthering the cause of human rights such as freedom and equality, Alwaqaa (2019a) argues that social action can be effected through the masterful use of literary language. Sexton's work may be located primarily at one point in this process, or she may travel through a number of stages in the course of a lifetime of work.

In the first stage of language revisionist process, the female writer accepts the definition of self and a prefabricated identity ascribed to her by the dominant voice in the culture. In this culture that voice is white, male and authoritative. The female individual in this stage is entirely oppressed and reduced because she is unconscious of the contradictions in which she lives and which she has thoroughly internalized. The second revisionist step is called dual consciousness, in which the

woman is aware of two contradictory definitions of self and identity. The first one is imposed from outside actually by patriarchy, which defines the way she is supposed to act, and the second one is a growing sense of self that contradicts that earlier definition or the imposed identity. DuBois (1965) comments on this consciously double existence. He writes, "It is a peculiar sensation, this double-consciousness, this sense of always looking at oneself through the eyes of others" (p. 16). Stage three of language revisionist strategy towards establishing one's identity is the beginning of redefinition and self-exploration. Renaming begins with unnamings as the poet stands apart and separates out the false or other-defined self and brings it to limelight by pointing out its fallacy and invalidity. As the female poet specifies and spots the false self and recognizes male-imposed identity, then she is simultaneously unnamings it, cancels it out part by part. Therefore, unnamings is a central and necessary step to the process of renaming.

Although this stage is uncomfortable and sometimes excruciating as the individual gives up parts and qualities of her former self that are no longer useful. The stage of unnamings is difficult and dangerous as it involves a courageous confrontation of the false self and the beginning of constructing a new one. This process is frequently painful and at the same time daring. Unnamings is somehow frightening because traditional concepts and taboos are being scorned and spurned away. In this respect Rich (1979a) writes.

The void is the creatrix, the matrix. It is not mere hollowness and anarchy. But in women it has been identified with lovelessness, barrenness, sterility. We have been urged to fill our 'emptiness' with children. We are not supposed to go down into the darkness of the core. Yet, if we can risk it, the something born of that nothing is the beginning of our truth (p. 191).

The fourth stage in the process of establishing a new female identity involves redefining and renaming the self. The female individual connects parts of the self and puts the self back together emanating from self-discovery and then self-identification. There is exhilaration and exuberance at the beginning of naming, where the female poet reclaims language, mythology and history as well as her self. In the last stage of identity construction, the renamed self renames the world and finds a new balance. She brings the world, through language, into an alignment with the new designated self.

Most of Sexton's poetry is at the stage of unnamings, of recognizing and cancelling out the other defined self. "The Double Image," for example, is a poem of unnamings, since the speaker labors hard to exorcize her mother in herself. Thus, the pain of her poetry comes from her unsuccessful

attempts to rename one's self and then the world around. She tries to throw away her older self and give birth to a new one, but in every trial, she fails coming back to the same place and the same face. She seems to be in a pit trying to climb up the sides, slipping and falling back to the bottom again and again until she is exhausted and cannot do it anymore. She does not break through from unnamings to renaming at least partly because of her profound isolation from other women, and to some extent of the patriarchal constraints to spell out her identity. In poem after poem, it is clear that she sees herself struggling alone with a male defined tradition of poetry within a society that is at large patriarchal. She is isolated temporally from a female tradition and spatially from a community of women because of her constant mental illness that kept her in a mental asylum for most of the time. Though she herself does not make it, her poetry does. Her struggle to survive has had a deep and continuing effect on the women poets who write after her.

Her poetry is distinguished by a tension or dialectic between dismantling the old concepts, images, and traditions and then piecing them together in new, different and fresh ways that provide an opportunity to woman's self-assertion and recognition. A creative tension around identity is at the center of the work of this poet. Her poetry is both individual and political not only in the sense that the personal is political and that; therefore, the poet, in expressing her particular reality, is engaged in a political and social act, not only in the sense that art is inevitably political in that it emerges from and expresses the social dynamics and tensions of a given age and place, but in the very specific sense that it is conscious of itself as coming out of a triple female experience of oppression, womanhood, and otherness.

One of the most oppressive concepts and images that patriarchy has invented is the ladyship ideal in order to blur and confuse women's real identity. Sexton has to fight to transform the image of lady found in Plath's poetry. This lady image is one of the more oppressive stereotypes a woman has to encounter and subdue. In this image women are soft, gentle, Christian, graceful, sweetly maternal and nurturing, fluffy headed, incompetent, gracious, small and weak, quiet and polite. So, society strives to maintain this cluster of images and qualities that add up to lady in order to guarantee its hegemony and exploitation with its typical instructions: ladies do this, ladies do not do that, be a little lady now, and so on. The concept of Lady is synonymous with the kind of woman supposed to be in Western culture. It is middle to upper middle class, white, idealized blond woman. Ladyship upholds the superiority of man as it is created by a patriarchal society. Therefore, to change this patriarchal structure is tied up with the need to change the language and social attitude towards such concepts. The new definition and identity that Sexton assumes does not

totally expel the image of ladyship; rather it is an essential facet in the construction of the new identity.

Moreover, the doll image created by patriarchy is another oppressive one closely connected to the concept of ladyship that women are forced to emulate. These Western images are designed to subordinate women and deprive them of an authentic identity. Society demands woman to be the beautiful, perfected doll, and her dead body should wear the smile of accomplishment. A doll has become the ultimate epitome of womanly perfection in society. Many female poets project this social prefabricated doll ideal that a woman should embrace. This image of woman should consist of voluptuous breasts, a tiny waist, curvy hips, long legs, and she is always smiling happily with no serious thoughts running around in her head. Marge Piercy, (1973) for example, captures this female persona perfectly in her poem titled "Barbie Doll," "She was advised to play coy, / exhorted to come on hearty, / exercise, diet, smile and wheedle" (pp. 25-26). So, Barbie is an object; beautiful on the outside and empty on the inside irrespective of whoever her purchaser decides her to be; a mother, a teacher, a nurse, or a model. Yet, one must remember that Barbie is not real. She is only an artificial construction made of plastic by man. Garry Leonard (1992) states: "A body 'isn't necessarily a figure' because a perfect figure would in fact be a dead body!" (p. 61).

Sexton's time of existence was not about asking questions about the nature of her roles. His time was about looking pretty and keeping quiet. Yet, she was a woman who had a difficult time keeping her mouth closed. Her poetry and her life tell another story. The doll image of beauty and perfection that society projects upon women haunted this poet who tries hard to shatter this image and to tackle the disappearance of both beauty and youth in her poetry. For instance, Sexton's poem "Woman with Girdle" deals ironically with the concept of aging and how to solve this problem facing women in advanced age. So, surgery and girdles seem to be the society's concoctions for these aging women to remain the perfect and doll-like ideal. In this poem, what the woman actually wants is to physically remove old skin through a surgery. The picture is disturbing and disgusting as an old woman is subject to a painful beauty surgery to her face so as to live up to the society's doll-like image of woman who should be "Pink and smooth as a baby." She wants youth and beauty forever to remain a doll of society. The images of an old woman undergoing a body surgery are starkly carnal and terrible.

Your midriff sags toward your knees;
your breasts lie down in air,
their nipples as uninvolved

as warm starfish (CPS, p. 70).

It seems that Sexton's plain message conveyed to women is that this gradual decay is the natural course of life. Gravity and time will take hold of a body and transform it, and there is no escape. It is as if she is asking the question: why does a woman have to tear off her flesh and place herself in a contraption to have a baby-like skin? To Sexton, these ideologies about beauty and medical techniques to make it everlasting do not make any sense. Therefore, a woman should not have to remain in a doll-like state for beauty and irrationally suffer for the purpose of being accepted by the world and to live up to the image and identity the patriarchal society has carved out for her.

Likewise, Sexton's speaker in her poem, "Self in 1958," lives in a society without a female-defined identity. The poem opens up with a perplexed female speaker asking,

What is reality?

I am a plaster doll; I pose
with eyes that cut open without landfall or nightfall
upon some shellacked and grinning person,
eyes that open, blue, steel, and close.

Am I approximately an I. Magnin transplant? (CPS, p. 155)

Instead of a real woman with blood and flesh and volition to decide her existence, the speaker is rather a "plaster doll" who "poses." The lack of identity and lost self is highlighted by the question, "Am I approximately an I. Magnin transplant?" Magnin & Company was an American fashion and luxury goods store that sells Madame Alexander dolls, a collection of dolls which predates Barbie by several decades and has the typical image of femininity with fancy clothes, perfectly styled hair, large eyes, and a dainty red mouth.

The speaker thus feels like a fake construction, a heartless toy, living an inauthentic existence. It is further illustrated in the second stanza.

I live in a doll's house
with four chairs,
a counterfeit table a flat roof
and a big front door.
Many have come to such a small crossroad.
There is an iron bed,
(Life enlarges, life takes aim)
a cardboard floor,

windows that flash open someone's city,
and little more (CPS, p. 155).

In these lines the poet's life in the outskirts setting is just as the construction and counterfeit as her identity and self, and her home furniture reveals a contrast picture that has a multiplicity of connotations; an "iron bed" and "a cardboard floor." An "iron bed" contrasts with the previous child-like images, and a cardboard floor suggests the fragile structure of woman's life that can give way at any moment. The line that the windows "flash open on someone's city, and little more" enhances the person's sense of alienation and lack of identity within a society dominated by males; the city is not her city, and she does not belong to it because it is "someone else's city," and beyond that the surroundings have little to offer her. Despite her feelings of alienation, loss and confusion, the painful realization that the statement "Many have come to such a small crossroad" implies that she is aware that there are other women who may feel as she does. This provides no solace and does nothing to lessen her feelings of confinement and subordination. Rather, being conscious that there are possibly other females undergoing the same emotional and psychological trauma like hers, seems to aggravate her despair. They are all suffering alone and no comfort whatsoever will be given.

The speaker's argument of being a toy produced by society for the sake of males' recreation and gratification carries on in the following stanza.

Someone plays with me,
plants me in the all-electric kitchen,
is this what Mrs. Rombauer said?
Someone pretends with me –
I am walled in solid by their noise –
or puts me upon their straight bed.
They think I am me!
Their warmth? Their warmth is not a friend!
They pry my mouth for their cups of gin
And their stale bread (CPS, p. 156).

Metaphorically, someone, maybe a man or a husband, "plays" with her emotions, "plants" her in the kitchen like a mannequin. So, the picture of the traditional roles for women is grim and awesome. Here Sexton, through the image of a doll, portrays the patriarchal exploitation of women and the complete control of their life. The use of action verbs prevalent throughout the poem

enhances the male ideology that women's destiny and identity is at the hand of man. The reference to the "all-electric kitchen" points to a modern house and woman's domestic duties that seems apparently a bliss for her, but in reality, this new technology exacerbates women's plight who has become one of these culinary electric gadgets. The sarcastic reference to "Mrs. Rombauer" brings to mind Irma Rombauer, the author of *The Joy of Cooking*, which was a popular American cookbook since its publication in 1931. This fleeting mention of this domestic female writer adds to the domestic theme in the poem and serves as a symbol for those women who are still deceived by and conform to the orthodoxy of man.

Thus, the speaker does not paint a portrait of domestic felicity. Again, someone plays with her by wearing a mask, by pretending with her, and she is deceitfully imprisoned by being "walled in solid by their noise" and forcibly put "upon their straight bed." This portrayal of her life sounds much more like that of an unwilling, abused captive or an asylum inmate than a happy housewife. However, the shock that "They think I am me!" suggests that the people around her do not consider this condition as strange or unusual, rather it is in compatibility with the patriarchal policy. It is only the speaker who is aware of her existence as a doll, and she suffers from the lack of a reliable identity. The hegemony of man and his over-towering domination over woman's life is enhanced by images such as "puts me upon their straight bed," "Their warmth is not a friend!" and "They pry my mouth." These activities are not welcome in the light of the words being employed. They present a description of a sexual and psychological violation. While bread is commonly considered to be a symbol of nourishment and life, in this poem the bread is stale, and unwholesome. There is no physical, emotional or spiritual comfort whatsoever to be found in this kind of selfish relationship. The employment of symbolism in Sexton's poetry is very effective as symbolism, according to Mujahid Alwaqaa (2019b), is considered a powerful weapon at the hands of skillful artists.

The unreality of the speaker's life is spotlighted by the frequent repetition of her dilemma in the next stanza.

What is reality
to this synthetic doll
who should smile, who should shift gears,
should spring the doors open in a wholesome disorder,
and have no evidence of ruin or fears?
But I would cry

rooted into the wall that
was once my mother
if I could remember how
and if I have the tears (CPS, p. 156).

The repetition of the word "should" points to expectations placed upon women in this role, who should "smile" and play the happy housewife. The speaker's longing for "the wall that was once my mother" points to the feelings of abandonment and alienation and of being overwhelmingly manipulated by a male community. The concluding lines of the poem end with a note of total despair and the tone is exceedingly mournful as the speaker longs for moments to cry if she only could remember how and if she had the tears. Furthermore, these lines suggest that she has been buried in the housewife role for so long that she does not remember how to show feelings of anguish, suffering and pain, as these emotions are not expected to emanate from a woman whose natural and conventional destiny is within the four walls of a house. Perhaps she simply cannot cry because she has been reduced to a doll, and displaying such emotions are beyond the ability of such a lifeless object. Space, here, represented by house acts as a prison for the female agency instead of a place where she feels a wider identification and empathy with it (Alwaqaa, 2021).

A fragmented self is ubiquitously evident in "Self in 1958," which glaringly portrays an upsetting portrait of a woman who feels excessively disappointed and sees her domestic existence inauthentic and shadow-like. However, this domestic sphere is traditionally recognized as the only reality of women existence. From biographical information about Sexton the reader gets to know that she did often feel stifled by her life as a wife and mother, and this resulted in the identity crisis in her life that culminates in self-destruction. Janice Markey (1988) states that the speaker in this poem stands for "the prototype of the all-American women put forward by the mass media of the period. She, in comparison to the woman in "Her Kind", does not have any sense of identity" (p. 150). Sexton (1985) again divulges her feelings towards the difficulty of leading a life governed by the laws and conventions of patriarchy. She explains this before she commenced in writing poetry. She writes, "I was trying my damndest to lead a conventional life, for that was how I was brought up, and it was what my husband wanted of me. But one can't build little white picket fences to keep nightmares out" (p. 84). In "self in 1958" her predictable "nightmares" come to the surface, unraveling the tensions, perplexity, and bewilderment which female individuals may undergo and endure within the constrictions of a conventional life that perpetuates the identity plight and the fakeness of women's existence.

Sexton relies on her life and experiences for the themes of her poems. Her experiences incorporate personal as well as mythical memories. The adventures of each of her personae constitute a commentary on the woman's identity plight in this unfair and biased world. She weaves highly personal poems out of her sexual, emotional and even spiritual experiences with integrity and mastery. Her poetry should thematically and stylistically be read in the context of her unique experiences of gender and feminine. As Kamala Das (2013) remarks in the course of an interview, "A writer derives inspiration from his life, what else? A writer is like a mirror that has learnt to retain the image reflected in it. Indelible reflection. Those who do not write, retain nothing of life, ultimately. Life runs through their fingers like fine sand" (p. 57).

Conclusion

Anne Sexton tries to subvert the underlying foundations and ideology of the patriarchal oppositional system by blurring its boundaries and decreasing its gap. To do so is to create new possibilities for constructing a new viable female identity that can be imagined, defined and articulated not in relation to male's interests or patriarchal hierarchy, but on female principles and terms. The possible alternatives are, definitely, based on difference, abundance and changeability. The new female identity can be defined as non-oppositional, non-hierarchical and a different kind of difference. The ultimate goal of the poetry of the feminist poets such as Sexton is to make the opposite sides of modern culture meet. Sexton wants the existing gender contradictions to be totally fused into the crucible of humanity. It is possible to argue that such a strategy, however, utopian, may effectively work towards healing the severe split between genders found in the binary opposition. It provides new creative perspectives for redefining critical concepts such as identity, love, and power through poetic composition.

Some of Sexton's poems have been invested with a personal mythology and are peopled with her different relations, mother, husband, lovers, children, and friends in an attempt to define her self in relation to them. Her personality has become the raw material for her poetry, and she realizes that she is different from other people in terms of vocation. As she believes that the poet's raw material is not stone or clay; it is her personality and language. This belief, which may be applied to every creative writer, reflects the essential component of her poetry and indicates a direction to the understanding of her character. Her poetry is sometimes described as a sort of compulsion-neurosis whose main purport is to offer a kind of release, a safety-valve, for her emotions. However, she views poetry as a means of self-discovery and investigation. She states that as she writes she gets closer and closer to her true self.

Her poems carry the violent energy associated with spontaneous and unreflected emotions. She finds poetry a demanding art. She uses, a personal voice, and self-revelation in an effort to evolve her personality in a self-assertive mood. It is observed that her personae are her own mutilated self, tormented by temporal consciousness of the loss of the self and identity. Thus, in Sexton's poetry, there is an abiding sense of identity crisis which pervades most of her poems as she relentlessly tries to build an identity in a patriarchal society. The existential framework of her poems underlines the dynamics of self-evolution. Her poetry is marked by a feminist consciousness as well as a feminist sense of resistance to male oppression.

The common major characteristic of Sexton's works is the confessional mode of her writing. She is seen as the modern model of the confessional feminist poet who transparently puts her heart naked on paper. Aside from her standard themes of depression, isolation, suicide, and despair; her work also encompasses feminist issues specific to women, such as struggle for identity, oppression by unsympathetic society, abortion, and more broadly adultery before such subjects were commonly addressed in poetic discourse. Currents of sufferings, social injustices and oppression overflow the whole of her poetry. She used her poetry to express the emotional anguish that characterized her life and the life of other women. She suffered several serious emotional and psychological setbacks. She was unable to be a mother and sank deeper into depression attempting suicide many times. Then she finally found an outlet in writing poetry to express the devastation in her life, the cruelty of an unfeeling husband, irresponsible parents and an unfair society at large.

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